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MILESTONE REPORT

TEST BEAM OF THE RADIATION HARD MONOLITHIC PROTOTYPES

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Abstract:

Milestone MS21 of WP5 (Development of Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors) consists of carrying out beam tests of radiation hard prototypes fabricated in the framework of the AIDAInnova project. This milestone has been successfully achieved and is reported in this document.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2024

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	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	N. Wermes F. Huegging S. Grinstein	UBonn UBonn IFAE	11/11/2024
Edited by	Sabrina El yacoubi	CERN	18/11/2024
Reviewed by	Daniela Bortoletto [Deputy Scientific coordinator]	UOXF	20/11/2024
Approved by	Daniela Bortoletto [Deputy Scientific coordinator]		25/11/2024

Executive summary

Earlier in the project Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors (DMAPS) that target devices capable of operating after large radiation doses were fabricated and characterized in the laboratory. This report documents the beam tests performed with different types of DMAPS developed within AIDAinnova, both before and after irradiation. The beam-tests were successfully completed and the data analysis will follow.

1. INTRODUCTION

Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel Detectors (DMAPS) are a key technology for the AIDAinnova project as they constitute, according to most detector experts, the most interesting new direction of pixel detector development and are therefore a key approach for pixel detectors at present and planned accelerator experiments.

Within WP5, the development strategy splits into two distinct targets. One focuses on high-granularity devices, with an emphasis on achieving small pixel dimensions, while the other prioritizes radiation hardness, particularly for applications at hadron colliders like the LHC. Despite these differing focuses, both approaches aim to deliver optimal performance in terms of position resolution (via small pixel size) and radiation tolerance. This document reports on the beam tests conducted with four different DMAPS prototypes:

LF-Monopix2 sensors fabricated in 150 nm CMOS technology represent a mature, large-scale prototype that incorporates a complete readout architecture.

TJ-Monopix2 sensors, built using 180 nm technology, share the digital readout design with the LF-Monopix2 but employ a small electrode approach.

MALTA2 sensors, also in 180 nm technology, were initially designed with small electrodes but were studied after exposure to large radiation doses.

RD50-MPW4 sensors in 150 nm technology are a recent development stemming from an exploratory effort.

This milestone report focuses on the progress and achievements made in these developments.

2. RADIATION HARD DMAPS PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT

The development of Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel sensors has followed so far two different design approaches (Fig. 2.1): (a) large electrode design and (b) small electrode design. While within AIDAinnova (a) is the prime approach for high radiation hardness, (b) targets primarily high granularity, i.e. small pixels, and low-noise and low-power operation, albeit with good radiation tolerance as well.

The large electrode design benefits charge collection, making, in principle, the approach intrinsically more radiation hard, which is critical for certain applications, in particular in inner layers of tracking detectors in hadron collider experiments. However, the downside of large electrodes is their larger capacitance at the input of the pre-amplifiers, resulting in larger noise and power consumption. Therefore, development efforts focus on achieving radiation-tolerant full charge

collection while trying to ensure a large signal-to-noise ratio for high hit-detection efficiency after irradiation.

Fig. 2.1 Two approaches for DMAPS: (a) large electrode cell design, (b) small electrode cell design.

2.1. TESTBEAM OF PROTOTYPE SENSORS LF-MONOPIX2 IN 150 NM TECHNOLOGY AND TJ-MONOPIX2 IN 180 NM TECHNOLOGY

The LF-Monopix2 chip fabricated in the 150 nm technology has a size of $1 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ and a pixel pitch of $50 \times 150 \mu\text{m}^2$ [1]. The pixel matrix takes up 82% of the chip area, while the rest is occupied by guard rings, decoupling capacitors and peripheral circuitry at the top and bottom of the chip. The large electrodes implemented in this prototype should result in an excellent performance after irradiation.

TJ-Monopix2 ($2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$) is developed in the 180 nm technology offered by Tower-Jazz and share common front-end (charge collecting structure) with the MALTA chips, which are fabricated in the same technology. It employs an established column-drain-type readout architecture similar to LF-Monopix2 chips, while benefiting from the smaller pixel size of $33 \times 33 \mu\text{m}^2$ with 512×512 pixel. Although not specifically designed for high radiation applications it shows good performance after irradiation.

Several beam tests of LF-Monopix2 and TJ-Monopix2 were carried out together at the DESY test beam facility with 6 GeV electrons [2, 3]. A first test beam with irradiated TJ-Monopix2, along with further studies with irradiated LF-Monopix2 devices took place in July 2024. The samples included proton-irradiated TJ-Monopix2 with a fluence of $5 \times 10^{14} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$, X-ray irradiated TJ-Monopix2 with a total ionizing dose of 100 MRad as well as neutron- and proton-irradiated LF-Monopix2 at fluence levels of 1×10^{15} and $2 \times 10^{15} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$.

The setup depicted in Fig. 2.1.1 included a telescope with six Mimoso26 planes for high spatial resolution and an external time reference plane (ATLAS ITkPix) with 25ns track time stamping capabilities. The devices were mounted in a Styrofoam box flooded with cooled nitrogen for temperature control. A feedback loop ensured temperature stability in the box of less than 1 K at temperatures below -10°C . More beam tests were conducted in the second half of 2024.

Fig. 2.1.1: Photography of the test beam setup with telescope and cooling box of the LF-Monopix2 and TJ-Monopix2 at DESY.

Apart from hit detection efficiency measurements, the temperature dependence, timing response and variation of the matrix flavor have been successfully studied. For all tested samples, the hit detection efficiency is above 98 % for all fluence and TID levels. More results will follow after the detailed analysis of the recorded data.

2.2. TEST BEAM OF PROTOTYPE MALTA2 IN 180 NM TECHNOLOGY

The MALTA series of depleted monolithic active-pixel sensors (DMAPS) was designed for potential use in the ATLAS experiment at the high-luminosity LHC (HL-LHC). These sensors are manufactured in the TowerJazz 180 nm CMOS imaging process, with additional process modifications to enhance the lateral electric field at the pixel corners to increase radiation tolerance [4].

The MALTA prototypes were successfully tested in multiple beam tests carried out at the SPS between 2022 and 2024, both before and after irradiation [5], as illustrated in Fig. 2.2.1. Additionally, the excellent position resolution of these devices made these devices highly effective as part of the MALTA telescope, a tool widely utilized by the community during beam tests at CERN.

Fig. 2.2.1: Beam tests of MALTA2 at CERN SPS during 2022. The photograph also shows the telescope planes composed of MALTA sensors.

2.3. TEST BEAM OF PROTOTYPE RD50-MPW4 IN 150 NM TECHNOLOGY

A second effort to develop radiation hard devices was launched after the LF-Monopix approach. The RD50-MPW4 chip [6] was recently (Jan 2024) fabricated in the framework of AIDAinnova, after multiple iterations to solve issues which affected earlier versions.

The RD50-MPW4 prototype consists of a matrix of 64×64 pixels each $62 \times 62 \mu\text{m}^2$. The analogue and digital readout are embedded in the sensing area. The chip implements a double column scheme to alleviate routing congestion and minimize crosstalk.

Beam tests were conducted in 2024 to evaluate its performance. Initial tests, performed before irradiation at DESY in April (Fig. 2.3.1), demonstrated that backside processing enables higher bias voltages and improved threshold settings. After irradiation, the devices underwent further testing at DESY in October 2024 (Fig. 2.3.2) [7].

Fig. 2.3.1: Beam tests of RD50-MPW4 at DESY on April 2024, when devices before irradiation were tested with a high energy electrons.

Fig.2.3.2: Photographs of the beam tests of RD50-MPW4 at DESY on October 2024. Irradiated devices were studied in this period.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The beam tests for the DMAPS developed in the context of the AIDAInnova project were executed as originally planned, achieving the following outcomes:

- Large prototype matrices, the LF-Monopix2 and TJ-Monopix2 were studied in detail after irradiation to fluencies up to $2 \times 10^{15} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$ and $5 \times 10^{14} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$, respectively, at the DESY test beam facility.
- The MALTA2 devices were tested in various beam tests before and after irradiation (up to a fluence of $3 \times 10^{15} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$) and the data analysis is underway.
- The RD50-MPW4 prototype was finally successfully tested in the laboratory and beam tests were conducted before and after irradiation at DESY in 2024.

The analysis of the beam tests are at an advanced stage (in the case of the LF-Monopix2, TJ Monopix2 and MALTA2) or starting (for the RD50-MPW4 device). We conclude that the beam tests were successfully completed, fully achieving milestone M21.

4. REFERENCES

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
DMAPS	Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors